

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

A meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held in Dean's chamber of College of Physiotherapy, City campus, Pandeshwar on **18.07.2022**.

The following members were present:

Dr. Rajasekar S - Chairperson
Dr. Thrishala Noronha - Member
Dr. Pathak Anupama - Member

PP
Thrishala
Anupama

Leave of absence:

Leave of absence was granted to

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member)

Dr. Bhargav Dave (External member) and

Dr. K. Vijay Kumar (External member) by the Chairperson, Board of Studies.

The Chairman welcomed all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting was thereafter deliberated by Dr. Thrishala Noronha on agenda items as had been approved by the Chairperson.

AGENDA

1. Addition of open electives for the BPT course.

2. Revision of credits and exam scheme.

1. Addition of open electives for the BPT course.

- Open electives for the BPT course offered by other departments have been specified and added under the semester tables.

Sl. No	Course Code	Course Name	Modification
1.	21BHMCT19	Food and Beverage etiquette	Added under the first semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks Credits – 2
2.	21BSW13 (B)	Youth development through social work	Added under the first semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks Credits – 2

3.	21BAJ23 (A)	Disaster Management	Added under the second semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits - 3.
4.	21BCMHN34-E3	Event Management	Added under the second semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits - 3.
5.	21BAJ03 (A)	Early childhood development	Added under the third semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits - 3.
6.	21BBAHN14	Personality Development-	Added under the third semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits – 3
7.	21BHMCT29	Food science and nutrition	Added under the fourth semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits – 3
8.	21BSW33 (B)	E-Business	Added under the fourth semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits – 3
9.	21BBAHN44	Personal wealth management	Added under the fourth semester table. Exam scheme – IA – 50 marks University exam - 50 marks Credits – 3

2. Revision of credits and exam scheme of courses from 2nd through 8th semester.

- Since certain courses' exam scheme and credits had to be revised as per the UGC recommendation and changes are as follows.

-Resolution: The members considered the curriculum and syllabus for BPT and discussed different issues. Finally, it was approved and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

Sl. No	Course Code	Course Name	Modification
1.	21BPTAECC05	Environmental sciences	Exam scheme IA- 50 marks Credits - 2
2.	21BPTSEC03	Basic nursing and first aid	Exam scheme IA- 50 marks
3.	Second semester total credits revised from 26 to 28		
4.	21BPTDSC07	Pathology and microbiology for physiotherapist	Credits changed from 4 to 3
5.	21BPTSEC05	Basic life support (BLS)	Exam scheme IA- 50 marks

6.	21BPTSEC07	Professional ethics	Exam scheme IA- 50 marks
7.	Third semester total credits revised from 26 to 28		
8.	21BPTDSC12	Electro physical agents I and II	Credits changed from 6 to 5
9.	Fourth semester total credits revised from 26 to 28		
10.	21BPTSEC09	Mobilizations and manipulations (peripheral and spinal joints)	Credits changed from 2 to 3
11.	21BPTSEC10	Clinical training – I	Exam scheme IA- changed from 50 to 100
12.	21BPTSEC11	Yoga	Credits changed from 2 to 3
13.	Fifth semester total credits revised from 26 to 28		
14.	21BPTDSE02	Women's health for physiotherapists	Credits changed from 3 to 4
15.	21BPTSEC12	Clinical training – II	Exam scheme IA- changed from 50 to 100
16.	Sixth semester total credits revised from 24 to 25		
17.	21BPTDSC21	Evidence based practice in physiotherapy	Exam scheme IA- 50 only Credits – changed from 3 to 2
18.	21BPTDSE03	Electrodiagnosis for physiotherapists	Exam scheme IA- 50 only
19.	21BPTDSE05	Research methodology and biostatistics	Credits changed from 2 to 3
20.	21BPTVOC03	Essentials of orthotics and prosthetics	Exam scheme IA- 50 only
21.	21BPTSEC14	Clinical training – III	Exam scheme IA- changed from 50 to 100
22.	21BPTDSC23	Community based rehabilitation (CBR)	Credits changed from 4 to 5
23.	21BPTDSE08	Research project	Exam scheme IA – 50 Exam – 50 (viva)
24.	21BPTSEC15	Clinical training – IV	Exam scheme IA- changed from 50 to 100
25.	Eighth semester total credits revised from 26 to 27		

The meeting started at 09.00 am and ended at 10:30 am with Thanks to the Chair.

Dr. Rajasekar S
CHAIRPERSON (BOS)

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE